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Deliverable D4.1:

Project Management Handbook

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Abstract

This Project Management Handbook is intended to support partners in the effective and efficient administration, procedural and financial management of the project. It focuses on project implementation procedures, structures and coordination and sets out key responsibilities for EU engagement and interaction. It is intended to support the achievement of project objectives, the effective management of partner progress and the timely delivery of project results.

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0.2	30/11/2023	Andrea Biancini (EITD)	Accepted small revisions from partners. Added the following sections: decision making process, contact list and preparation and organization of meetings.
0.3	20/02/2024	Andrea Biancini (EITD)	Updated section regarding internal reports to align with interim report to the founding institution.
0.4	11/04/2025	Romane Léauté (EITD)	Restructured deliverable according to PO comments during review meeting.
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Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	6
1.1	SPECTRO	6
1.2	Work Package 4	7
1.3	Deliverable 4.1.....	7
1.3.1	Purpose	7
1.3.2	Objectives.....	7
2	Management of SPECTRO project.....	8
2.1	Management structure.....	8
2.1.1	General Assembly (GEA)	9
2.1.2	Project Coordinator (PC).....	10
2.1.3	Project Manager (PM).....	10
2.1.4	Project Executive Committee (PEC).....	11
2.1.5	Quality Manager (QM).....	11
2.1.6	Work Package Leaders (WPL).....	11
2.1.7	Task Leaders (TL).....	11
2.1.8	Project Communication Officer (PCO).....	12
2.1.9	Project roles.....	12
2.1.10	Project contacts list.....	13
2.2	Preparation and organization of meetings.....	14
2.2.1	Convening meetings.....	14
2.2.2	Notice of a meeting	15
2.2.3	Sending the agenda.....	16
2.2.4	Minutes of meetings.....	16
2.3	Decision Making Process.....	16
2.3.1	Decision process.....	16
2.3.2	Conflict resolution	17
2.4	Project Workplan & Implementation	17
2.4.1	Work Plan.....	18
2.4.2	Project Deliverables.....	18
2.4.3	Project Milestones	21

3	Project reporting	22
3.1	Formal reporting to EC	22
3.2	Internal reporting	23
4	Working methods	24
4.1	Internal communication.....	25
4.1.1	Communication platform.....	25
4.1.2	Video conferences.....	25
4.1.3	Face-to-face meetings.....	25
4.2	Document sharing and storage.....	25
4.3	Presentations	26
5	Quality Control	26
5.1	Deliverables.....	27
6	Financial support to students	27
6.1	Eligible countries	27
6.2	Eligible recipients	27
6.3	Activities to be founded	27
6.4	Maximum amount per student and criteria for its determination	28
6.5	Minimum number of students	29
6.6	How to apply	29
6.7	Awarding criteria	30
6.7.1	Promotion of diversity	31
	Appendix A – Template for progress report.....	32
	Appendix B – Template for reporting expenses	33

Table of Figures

Figure 1: SPECTRO Project Management Structure.....	8
Figure 2: List of internal meetings	15
Figure 3: EC Reporting periods for the project	23

Table of Tables

Table 1: Key roles in the management of SPECTRO project.	9
Table 2: SPECTRO partners contact list	13
Table 3: List of recurrent meetings.....	14
Table 4: Schema of notice period for meetings.....	16
Table 5: Agenda anticipation for project meetings.	16
Table 6: List of deliverables	20
Table 7: List of milestones	22

1 Introduction

This Project Management Handbook is intended to support partners in the effective and efficient administration, procedural and financial management of the project. It focuses on project implementation procedures, structures and coordination and sets out key responsibilities for EU engagement and interaction. It is intended to support the achievement of project objectives, the effective management of partner progress and the timely delivery of project results.

This Project Management Handbook sets out:

- the procedures and standards to be used in the SPECTRO project;
- the key roles and responsibilities;
- how the project will be carried out, measured, monitored, accounted for and safeguarded during the project.

1.1 SPECTRO

SPecialised Education programmes in CybersecuriTy and Robotics (SPECTRO) will focus on the design and delivery of two double-degree master's programmes (ISCED Level 7, 120 ECTS) in two key digital technology areas for the future of Europe:

- 1) Cybersecurity, and
- 2) Robotics.

The two specialised master's programmes, which will also include a minor in Innovation and Entrepreneurship, will be designed and delivered by a consortium consisting of 12 higher education institutions (7 of which involved in Cybersecurity and 8 in Robotics) from 7 different countries, 2 innovative SMEs, 1 leading research centre in Information Systems and EIT Digital, a pan-European organisation with in-depth knowledge and experience in the digital skills domain. In 2025, two additional higher education institutions joined the consortium as Associated partners. The consortium now counts 14 higher education institutions from 8 different countries. The master's programmes developed by SPECTRO partners will address the labour market needs, foster strong interactions and mobility between academia and business, strengthen knowledge triangle integration, promote entrepreneurship, and considerably boost the growth of the existing EIT Digital ecosystem, one of the largest digital ecosystems in Europe. In addition to the two master's programme, SPECTRO partners will also develop and deploy a series of self-standing learning modules on topics related to Cybersecurity and Robotics. These modules will lead to four different certifications, which will be released by participating higher education institutions and EIT Digital.

Dedicated marketing, promotion, communication, and dissemination activities will be carried out by SPECTRO partners to maximise the outreach of project activities and to attract the desired target audience to the master's programmes and self-standing modules. SPECTRO will expand the specialised education offer in Europe and will contribute to reducing the current shortage of digital specialists in Europe, by providing training to more than 1000 European citizens in Cybersecurity and Robotics.

1.2 Work Package 4

The objectives of Work Package 4 are:

- To ensure the overall management of the project and effectively monitor the project, in administrative, technical, and financial terms.
- To guarantee high-quality content and management with the aim of securing effective progress.
- To coordinate the enrolment process of participants to SPECTRO education programmes.
- To ensure the establishment of effective and sustainable partnerships within the consortium.

It is concerned with undertaking the technical and scientific coordination of the SPECTRO project as well as the administrative and financial management. This work package will ensure that appropriate quality control and reporting mechanism are applied across the project.

1.3 Deliverable 4.1

1.3.1 Purpose

The SPECTRO Project Handbook has been prepared with two purposes:

1. to provide the framework within which the project will be managed by the coordinator;
2. to guide project participants through all aspects of the project's management and coordination activities and provide a clear set of rules and expectations to be followed in conducting the project.

1.3.2 Objectives

- To define the procedures and standards to be used in the SPECTRO project.
- To define key roles and responsibilities.
- To demonstrate how the project will be carried out, measured, monitored, accounted for and safeguarded during the project.

2 Management of SPECTRO project

2.1 Management structure

SPECTRO implementation work plan requires effective project management to deliver high quality results. The project management approach chosen guarantees transparency and commitment to all partners and facilitates successful project execution. Consortium bodies and key actors in the management structure are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: SPECTRO Project Management Structure.

Table 1 provides a short description of the key roles in the consortium. Duties, responsibilities, and rights will be codified and agreed in the project Consortium Agreement.

Key roles	Acronym	Definition
General Assembly	GEA	Composed of consortium members; responsible for the project, including any significant changes.
Project Executive Committee	PEC	Composed of PC and WP Leaders, responsible for technical and operational management, quality, risk mitigation and progress tracking.
Project Coordinator	PC	Responsible for overall coordination, content management and liaisons with EC..

Key roles	Acronym	Definition
Project Manager	PM	Supporting the PC, responsible for administrative and financial progress reporting.
Quality Manager	QM	Responsible for Quality Plan creation and implementation and risk management.
Work Package Leader	WPL	Responsible for planning and progress in a WP and contributing to the PEC.
Task Leader	TL	Responsible for the planning and deployment of the specific actions defined under the task.
Project Communication Officer	PCO	Responsible for external communication activities.

Table 1: Key roles in the management of SPECTRO project.

2.1.1 General Assembly (GEA)

The GEA consists of management level representatives of all consortium partners, each having one vote. This is to ensure ownership of the results and to prove the commitment on all sides. It is chaired by the Project Coordinator. The GEA is the highest decision-making body in the project. It will assume overall responsibility for project conformance to the contract. The GEA deals with contractual issues escalated to it, or issues requiring GEA confirmation and/or voting according to the consortium agreement. The GEA ensures that the partners give continued support and adequate resources to the project; promotes the results of the project and acts as the final level of escalation, should serious conflicts arise during the project. In particular, the GEA is responsible for:

- Major changes to the consortium, work plan or budgets, especially if requiring EC approval.
- Review, quality check and approval of project deliverables and, more in general, of any public output
- Guaranteeing confidentiality of internal project results/outputs designated as restricted to the consortium.
- Establishing a controlling and reporting system for resource consumption and progress against schedule.

- GEA delegates, as representatives of contractors, are responsible for: 1) Submission of correct financial and administrative data to the Project Coordinator, 2) Commitment of their own organisations, including financial matters and management of their internal resources.

The role, decision responsibilities and powers of the GEA are specified in the Consortium Agreement.

2.1.2 Project Coordinator (PC)

The PC will cooperate and exchange information with the project management (PM) to guarantee the correct delivery and reporting of the project.

The PC is responsible for the management and coordination of the entire project. The PC also chairs and ensures proper operation of the key consortium bodies GEA and PEC. The PC reports to the GEA. Responsibilities include:

- Execution of all project obligations vis-à-vis the Agency, including submission of project deliverables.
- Acting as the intermediary between the partners and the EC / Project Officer (PO).
- Calling PEC / GEA meetings, informing and chairing PEC and GEA.
- Resolution of financial and contractual issues.
- Overseeing the implementation of administrative processes.

As the official interface between the consortium and the EC, the PC monitors project activities, maintains an up- to-date view of progress and will, where appropriate, suggest changes to the original work plan to ensure achievement of project objectives. The PC will be supported by the PM in ensuring all administrative objectives and obligations are met. In order to meet the scientific and technical goals, the PC is supported by WP Leaders in the context of the PEC.

2.1.3 Project Manager (PM)

The PM will work closely together with the PC function and ensures that the Project Coordinator receives all necessary support in coordination matters and in particular regarding annual cost statements, payments, budget allocations and audit certificates from each partner at the time of financial reporting. In addition, the PM is responsible for the following activities:

- Dealing with all administrative issues arising in the project including data collection from partners
- Preparing meetings with the project consortium, ensuring minutes are taken and approved.
- Supporting the communication with the EC in general, and with respect to the preparation of review meetings, and the submission and approval of deliverables.
- Financial Control: monitoring Financial Statements, feedback to the partners and the PC.

- External relations: receive external requests and questions on project, provide interested parties with information issued by the project, follow-up on cooperation with other projects, track events connected with relevant stakeholders and international forums.

2.1.4 Project Executive Committee (PEC)

The PEC is the project's driving force for project activities. It is chaired by the PC, reports to the GEA and is composed of WPL, WP Team members, QM, IM and the Quality Experts will be invited, in case their expertise is required. The PEC oversees project progress and in particular:

- Implementation of all action plans.
- Coordination of work package dependencies.
- Maintaining communication and ensuring reporting.
- Providing guidance on Intellectual Property issues.
- Supporting implementation of the quality assurance system.
- Ensuring guidance on ethical and (legal) data protection issues is followed.
- Creation of efficient team structures.
- Establishing flexible effective communication and an appropriate meeting schedule.

2.1.5 Quality Manager (QM)

The QM is responsible for the definition of the Quality Assurance Plan and its implementation by all partners. The QM will manage and coordinate the procedures to assess the quality of project deliverables and learning content for the short-term training programmes, appointing peer reviewers from the partners' staff to support the process.

2.1.6 Work Package Leaders (WPL)

Work Package Leaders are responsible for managing their WP as a self-contained entity, as well as managing interfaces to other WPs through the PEC. WPL coordinate, monitor, and assess the progress of the WP to ensure that output performance, budget, and timelines are met. Their responsibilities include:

- Production of project deliverables according to defined quality processes.
- Identifying risks to report to the Project Manager and complying with risk mitigation plans.
- Reporting quality issues and status to the Quality Manager.
- Achievement of the technical objectives of the project in their domain.
- Ensuring conformance of WP results with requirements of succeeding work packages

2.1.7 Task Leaders (TL)

Task leaders are responsible for managing their tasks as a self-contained entity, and in relation to other tasks part of the Work Package and of the project. Their responsibility include:

- Plan and deploy the activities related to the task in accordance with the project timeline.
- Contribute to the deliverables connected to their tasks.
- Identify and flag to the WPL any task related risks while proposing mitigation actions.

2.1.8 Project Communication Officer (PCO)

PCO will manage and coordinate all dissemination and outreach activities within SPECTRO project. The PCO will act as the single point of contact for partners for communication-related topics and will lead the communication and update meetings with partners to align on dissemination activities.

2.1.9 Project roles

In the context of the SPECTRO project, the assignment of roles and responsibilities across the different Work Packages (WPs) has been carefully aligned with the prior expertise and involvement of the participating institutions in relevant educational activities under the EIT Digital framework. The project budget has been built around this structure, with all costs, including personnel, aligned with the expected level of effort for each role.

Work Package 1 (WP1), dedicated to the education programme in Cybersecurity, has been entrusted to Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE). This decision builds on ELTE's longstanding role as the programme lead for Cybersecurity within the EIT Digital Master School, a function it has successfully fulfilled since before the launch of the SPECTRO project. This continuity ensures consistency in academic leadership and leverages ELTE's deep expertise in the field.

Similarly, Work Package 2 (WP2), which covers the education programme in Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots, has been assigned to the University of Trento (UNITN). Like ELTE, UNITN has been a key programme leader within the EIT Digital Master School, specifically for programmes on Autonomous Systems. Their appointment as WP2 leader reflects the project's strategy to capitalise on pre-existing academic leadership and technical excellence.

In line with the project's collaborative spirit and to ensure balanced workload distribution, the two tasks focusing on the creation of self-standing online learning modules—Task 1.2 on Cybersecurity and Task 2.2 on Robotics—have been assigned to institutions other than the WP leads but with strong domain relevance. The University of Turku (UTU) has taken responsibility for Task 1.2 due to its active involvement in the Cybersecurity education activities within the consortium, while the University of Bologna (UNIBO), with recognised strengths in Robotics and Autonomous Systems, leads Task 2.2. This deliberate allocation of responsibilities ensures that the project draws on the

strengths of different partners while enabling a broader engagement of institutions and a more equitable distribution of development efforts.

Work Packages 3 and 4, which focus on dissemination and communication (WP3) and project administration and implementation (WP4), respectively, are led by EIT Digital (EITD). EITD, as the project coordinator, is uniquely positioned to manage these transversal activities, having already overseen similar communication and administrative processes within the EIT Digital Master School ecosystem. Importantly, the core of the work in WP3 and WP4 does not involve creating new methodologies or deliverables from scratch. Rather, it centres on adapting established processes to the specific needs of the SPECTRO project, including student admissions, scholarship distribution, project meetings, deliverables coordination, and partner alignment. The most substantial effort in these WPs thus lies in executing and synchronising these complex processes efficiently across a diverse consortium.

Finally, to ensure objective oversight, the quality assurance function of the project has been explicitly entrusted to a partner external to EIT Digital. This measure safeguards the independence of the quality control mechanisms and avoids any potential conflict of interest between those implementing the project’s core processes and those responsible for verifying their quality.

2.1.10 Project contacts list

In order to streamline communication and foster collaboration, SPECTRO has one individual as contact point per organisation. General enquiries: all general enquiries about the SPECTRO project should be directed to spectro@eitdigital.eu

Organisation	Contact name
EIT Digital	Romane Léauté
Aalto University	Quan Zhou
Budapest University of Technology and Economics	Balint Kiss
Eötvös Loránd University	Viktoria Villany
Eurecom	Raphaël Troncy
KTH Royal Institute of Technology	Mihhail Matskin
Babeş-Bolyai University	Darius-Vasile Bufnea
University Côte d'Azur	Françoise Baude
University of Bologna	Giuseppe Notarstefano
University of Trento	Davide Brunelli
University of Rennes	Alvaro Stranger
University of Twente	Florian Hahn

Organisation	Contact name
University of Turku	Seppo Virtanen
Gim Robotics	Mika Vainio
Evolutionary Archetypes Consulting SL	Nektar Baziotis
University of the Aegean (Associate Partner)	Dimitrios Zisis
Polytechnic University of Bari (Associate Partner)	David Naso

Table 2: SPECTRO partners contact list

2.2 Preparation and organization of meetings

Meeting preparation and organization is described in the Grant Agreement agreed by all participants of the project. Here an extract of the relevant information regarding meeting described in the GA.

2.2.1 Convening meetings

As described in the project Grant Agreement, the following subsection presents the list of recurrent meetings as well as the list of internal meetings that have occurred or are planned.

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly (GEA)	Four meetings: 1 st - within first three month of year 1, 2 nd - within second half of year 2, 3 rd - within second half of year 3, 4 th - within second half of year 4.	At any time upon request of the Project Executive Committee or 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly
Project Executive Committee (PEC)	Monthly teleconferences. Face-to-face meeting organize every 6 months: in March and September of each project year.	At any time upon request of any Member of the General Assembly
General Assembly and Project Executive Committee	GEA and PEC will meet jointly at the beginning of the project for detailed strategy and planning.	
Work Package (WP)	Monthly for each WP.	At any time upon request of any Member of the WP or Project Coordinator

Table 3: List of recurrent meetings

N.	Type of meeting	Date
General Assembly (GEA) Year 1 (Project kick-off)	Ordinary	21-22 September 2023
General Assembly (GEA) Year 2	Ordinary	12 February 2024
General Assembly (GEA) Year 3	Ordinary	27 February 2025
General Assembly (GEA) Year 4	Ordinary	TBC in 2026
Extraordinary GEA	Extraordinary. Termination of the Cyscale partner and approval of the new project partner: Evolutionary Archetypes	Online on 28 January 2025
Extraordinary GEA	Extraordinary. Consortium meeting of partners following the project Interim review	Hybrid on 27 March 2025
Project Executive Committee (PEC) F2F meeting 1	Ordinary	16-17 April 2024
Project Executive Committee (PEC) F2F meeting 2	Ordinary	2 October 2024
Project Executive Committee (PEC) F2F meeting 3	Ordinary	9 April 2025
PEC meetings online	Ordinary	Last Tuesday of every month
WP1 & WP2 regular meetings	Ordinary	Monthly (dates vary)
WP3 regular meetings	Ordinary	Last Tuesday of every month
WP4 regular meetings	Ordinary	Last Wednesday of every month

Figure 2: List of internal meetings

2.2.2 Notice of a meeting

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall give written notice of a meeting to each Member of that Consortium Body as soon as possible and no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	30 calendar days	14 calendar days
Project Executive Committee	7 calendar days	4 calendar days
WP	7 calendar days	4 calendar days

Table 4: Schema of notice period for meetings.

2.2.3 Sending the agenda

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall prepare and send each Member of that Consortium Body an agenda no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

General Assembly	10 calendar days, 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Project Executive Committee	3 calendar days
WP	3 calendar days

Table 5: Agenda anticipation for project meetings.

2.2.4 Minutes of meetings

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall produce minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. He/she shall send the draft minutes to all Members within 5 calendar days of the meeting. The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 3 calendar days from receipt, no Member has sent an objection by written notice to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes by written notice. The chairperson shall send the accepted minutes to all the Parties and to the Coordinator, who shall retain copies of them.

2.3 Decision Making Process

The decision-making process, and the agreement on how to solve potential conflicts, is described in the Grant Agreement agreed by all participants of the project. Here an extract of the relevant information regarding the decision-making process.

2.3.1 Decision process

Decisions will be taken by the responsible team members, and organisation bodies based on the Description of Action (DoA) to be performed, as stated in the Grant Agreement, the Consortium Agreement, the DoA and the individual Work Package plans. In case there is a dispute between two or more team members, an agreement will be sought by informal communication. If no agreement is reached, the conflict resolution procedure will be resorted to.

2.3.2 Conflict resolution

Agreement on any issue with divergent views usually is to be reached through informal contact. This is to be followed by confirmation via email or in agreed written minutes for substantial issues. In some cases, the agreement may take the form of a short statement or report signed by those responsible. Technical issues/conflicts within given contractual commitments that do not involve a change of contract, a change of budget and/ or a change of resources/ overall focus will be discussed/ solved at the WP level first. Where a potential conflict is identified, the appropriate WPL will attempt to mediate between the parties. The PC must be informed if the solution affects the work plan and expected results or if no resolution is reached. In the latter case, the PC will make every effort to mediate, if necessary, involving other members of the PEC. Should the PEC not solve the conflict, the issue is referred to the GEA. The GEA will attempt to reach a unanimous decision in all cases. Should a consensus not be achieved, decisions will be reached by a simple majority vote, each delegate having one vote. Should a conflict not be resolved by this mechanism, the project coordinator will make a final decision on the matter after coordination with the EC PO. GEA delegates will ensure that decisions taken at the GEA are carried out by the participant they represent.

2.4 Project Workplan & Implementation

SPECTRO is broken into 4 WPs where each WP contains a set of associated and related tasks. The overall WP plan has been agreed by all parties and implements a commonly agreed work plan, deliverables, and milestones. The interlinkages and relationships between WP's are illustrated below.

The WPs have the following responsibilities and interfaces:

- **WP1:** Will deliver education programme in Cybersecurity consisting of a double degree master program and a number of self-standing learning modules. The education programme will meet the needs of the labour markets and will increase the number of citizens in Europe able to design, develop, and deploy digital solutions in the economy and across sectors.
- **WP2:** Will deliver education programme in Robotics consisting of a double degree master program and a number of self-standing learning modules. The education programme will meet the needs of the labour markets and will increase the number of citizens in Europe able to design, develop, and deploy digital solutions in the economy and across sectors.
- **WP3:** Will take responsibility for dissemination and communication activities. The WP will aim at ensuring the project results and outputs reach the relevant target audiences as widely as possible.
- **WP4:** Will undertake the technical and scientific coordination as well as the administrative and financial management. This WP will also ensure that quality control and reporting mechanism as being applied as required.

2.4.1 Work Plan

A full description of work plan, including Work Package tasks, deliverables and associated milestones is contain in the Grant Agreement Annex 1. This will be used as the main reference point for the project.

2.4.2 Project Deliverables

All project deliverables are associated with a specific work package task. It will be the responsibility of the task lead to co-ordinate the drafting of the deliverable and ensure the inputs of other partners where necessary. Table 6 provides an overview of all the deliverables, the lead partner and the deadlines for internal review and submission to the Commission.

N°	Name	WP n°	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D1.1	Master's programme in Cybersecurity: Curriculum Design	WP1	ELTE	R	PU	M12
D1.2	Report on education Cybersecurity programmes	WP1	UR1	R	PU	M24

N°	Name	WP n°	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
	results after the first year of delivery of programmes					
D1.3	Report on education Cybersecurity programmes results after the second year of delivery of programmes	WP1	UTU	R	PU	M36
D1.4	Report on education Cybersecurity programmes results after the third year of delivery of programmes	WP1	ELTE	R	PU	M48
D2.1	Master's programme in Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots: Curriculum Design	WP2	UNITN	R	PU	M12
D2.2	Report on Robotics education programmes results after the first year of delivery of programmes	WP2	UNBO	R	PU	M24
D2.3	Report on Robotics education programmes results after the second year of delivery of programmes	WP2	AALTO	R	PU	M36
D2.4	Report on Robotics education programmes results after the third year of delivery of programmes	WP2	UNITN	R	PU	M48
D3.1	Marketing and Dissemination Plan	WP3	EITD	R	PU	M6

N°	Name	WP n°	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D3.2	First year report on the marketing and dissemination activities	WP3	EITD	R	PU	M12
D3.3	Second year report on the marketing and dissemination activities	WP3	EITD	R	PU	M24
D3.4	Third year report on the marketing and dissemination activities	WP3	EITD	R	PU	M36
D3.5	Fourth year report on the marketing and dissemination activities	WP3	EITD	R	PU	M48
D4.1	Project Management Handbook	P4	EITD	R	PU	M6
D4.2	Data Management Plan	P4	EITD	R	PU	M6
D4.3	Quality Assurance Methodology	P4	UNITN	R	PU	M12
D4.4	Enrolment and scholarship allocation First year report	P4	EITD	R	SEN	M12
D4.5	Enrolment and scholarship allocation Second year report	P4	EITD	R	SEN	M24
D4.6	Enrolment Third year report	P4	EITD	R	SEN	M36
D4.7	Enrolment—Fourth year report	P4	EITD	R	SEN	M48
D4.8	Intermediate report on community, partnership, and mobility management	P4	EITD	R	SEN	M24

N°	Name	WP n°	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D4.9	Final report on community, partnership, and mobility management	P4	EITD	R	SEN	M48
D4.10	Quality Assurance Methodology Application	P4	UNITN	R	SEN	M48

Table 6: List of deliverables

2.4.3 Project Milestones

N°	Name	WP n°	Lead beneficiary	Due Date
MS1	Tentative curriculum of the master's programme defined.	WP1	ELTE	M3
MS2	Labour market needs analysis completed, and curriculum of the Cybersecurity master's programme finalised.	WP1	ELTE	M12
MS3	Cybersecurity learning modules, and related certification schemes completed.	WP1	UT	M16
MS4	First two-year cycle of the master's programme in Cybersecurity delivered.	WP1	EITD	M36
MS5	Second two-year cycle of the master's programme in Cybersecurity delivered.	WP1	EITD	M48
MS6	Tentative curriculum of the master's programme in Robotics defined.	WP2	UNITN	M3
MS7	Labour market needs analysis completed, curriculum of the master's programme in Robotics finalized.	WP2	UNITN	M12
MS8	Robotics learning modules and related certification schemes completed.	WP2	UNBO	M16
MS9	First two-year cycle of the master's programme in Robotics delivered.	WP2	EITD	M36
MS10	Second two-year cycle of the master's programme in Robotics delivered.	WP2	EITD	M48
MS11	Development of a Marketing and Dissemination Plan.	WP3	EITD	M4
MS12	Completion of the planned Marketing, Communication and Dissemination activities.	WP3	EITD	M47
MS13	Completion of Project Management Handbook.	WP4	EITD	M4
MS14	Definition of a Data Management Plan.	WP4	EITD	M4

N°	Name	WP n°	Lead beneficiary	Due Date
MS15	Definition of a Quality Assurance Principles.	WP4	UNITN	M6
MS16	Completion of the enrolment process of students for the first full cycle of master's programmes.	WP4	EITD	M10
MS17	Completion of the enrolment process of students for the second full cycle of master's programmes.	WP4	EITD	M22
MS18	Definition of an internship programme for master students.	WP4	EITD	M16

Table 7: List of milestones

3 Project reporting

3.1 Formal reporting to EC

Formal reporting to the EC is due after 18 and 36 months since project start and again at the end of the project (after four years). Reporting is carried out using the online platform provided by the EC which specify the required contents: in essence, a periodic technical report and a periodic financial report. These reports are required within 60 days of the end of the period.

Work Package leads are expected to contribute to the technical report, with input from all partners as needed. All funded partners must provide an individual financial statement detailing their eligible costs for the period.

The interim reporting to the EC will happen in the following periods:

- From month 1 to month 18 (September 2023 - February 2025)
- From month 19 to month 36 (March 2025 - August 2026)
- From month 37 to month 48 (September 2026 - August 2027)

As described in the Grant Agreement of the project these periods will be reported within 60 days after the period termination date.

Figure 3: EC Reporting periods for the project

3.2 Internal reporting

In parallel with the formal reporting to the EC, all partners will share interim information regarding efforts, expenses, and achievements in an internal report. The internal reporting process be aligned with the formal reporting to the EC and will permit the Coordinator, and all the partner, to:

1. Collect from all partners information regarding work performed on the project, results and impacts achieved.
2. Collect from all partners their financial statements forecast for the reporting period.
3. Compare project achievements with resource consumptions and confront them with the project plan.
4. Share main findings regarding project execution with all partners.

This internal reporting process will then ease the process of formal reporting by all partners and the production of a consolidated report for the project to be formally submitted to the EC during the interim reporting phases. It will also permit the project Consortium to provide the best representation of the efforts and achievement on the project.

The internal reporting will work on the same information to be collect and shared for the formal reporting to the EC, including:

- Brief written reports of the activities of the partner per work package.
- Updates on work on deliverables, risks, problems and planned activities.
- A summary of meetings attended.
- Expenses and financial activities.

A template that can support the reporting of this information is provided in Appendix A of this project handbook. The document can also be found on the WP4 workspace of the SPECTRO Team Drive. When requested, it is important that all participants use this template for the reporting to ease data reconciliation and correct reporting to the EC.

Moreover, core partners which lead work packages are asked to provide updates per task and an overview of the status of the deliverables and milestones. This will enable the PC to track effort and spend against plan and to detect any deviations early. The reporting of the activities in the different WP will be done during the monthly PEC meetings and will be registered in the minutes for such meetings.

The project's milestones (listed in Table 7) mark the completion of the significant activities of the project and are defined in the Grant Agreement. It is therefore important to report them in a timely fashion. Since each milestone is associated with one or more work packages, it is the responsibility of the Work Package leads to report to the PC on the achievement of the milestone when it becomes due (and not waiting for the periodic report to the EC). The PC will work with the PEC to ensure the reporting of milestones.

Regarding reporting for expenses and financial activities, this can include:

- The staff effort (person-months) expended in the preceding three months.
- A summary of all personal costs.
- A summary of non-staff costs such as travel, workshop costs etc.

A template for the reporting of this information is provided in Appendix B of this project handbook. The document can also be found on the WP4 workspace of the SPECTRO Team Drive. It is important that all participants use this template for the reporting to ease data reconciliation and correct reporting to the EC. The document also can be found on the WP4 workspace on the SPECTRO Team Drive. Project partners are free to use their own forms but have to keep in mind to include all the requirements that are stated in the instructions section of the template.

4 Working methods

With a high number of partners involved in the SPECTRO project, working methods to facilitate communication and project documentation managed and made available to all partners appropriately are of central importance. The communication tools and working methods introduced in the following sections together will contribute to a working environment in which project members can collaborate and work in a most efficient way.

4.1 Internal communication

Communication within the project will happen through different channels. Whilst face-to-face meetings will be held at a regular basis yet with a rather low frequency, there are a number of virtual communication channels through which project members including advisory bodies and WP teams can communicate on daily basis.

4.1.1 Communication platform

The platform used to support internal project communication is Microsoft Teams. In the Teams instance of EITD a specific space has been created for the SPECTRO project. This space enables users to have private conversations via real-time messaging, start, follow or contribute to discussions on the discussion platform, share documents and link documents saved in Sharepoint. Next to the project-wide environment there are also team environments for each work package. If needed, project members can set up additional channels, for instance if the completion of deliverables or milestones requires collaboration between WPs. All project members have access to all teams and documents unless specifically restricted.

Members new to the project should contact the PM to get an invitation to join the SPECTRO Teams. In order to join WP teams, project members are asked to contact the WP leaders of the respective WP.

4.1.2 Video conferences

Microsoft Teams is used as conferencing software for online meetings. Video conferences of managing bodies (such as the GEA, the PEC or WPL meetings) are held on Microsoft Teams.

4.1.3 Face-to-face meetings

Plenary meetings of the whole project will take place three times throughout the project's lifetime: at the beginning (kick-off meeting) and annually up to the end of the project. Every six months the members of the PEC will meet face-to-face to discuss advancements on the project and potential risks or issues. Smaller face-to-face meetings will be arranged back-to-back with major events. Additional face-to-face meetings will be undertaken on a work package or cross work package basis, or for other purposes as needed.

4.2 Document sharing and storage

The PC arranged for the project's own Microsoft Teams workspace. Documents can be stored, shared and collaboratively worked on in the Teams Drive. All documents created and uploaded

there will have SPECTRO as the document owner which ensures that all documents created for SPECTRO will be owned by the project. Project members including the advisory bodies get access to the project Team via Microsoft-associated personal or institutional email addresses.

4.3 Presentations

All presentations prepared for and given at internal meetings, such as face-to-face meetings and side meetings at conferences, will be stored in the SPECTRO Team Drive. Specificities about the presentation and formal content of external presentations will be covered in D3.1 “Marketing and Dissemination Plan”.

5 Quality Control

Quality control is essential for project management because it ensures that the project's processes and outputs meet defined standard. It helps identify and correct issues early, reducing the risk of, delays, ultimately improving efficiency, consistency, and the overall success of the project.

The Quality Assurance Methodology is detailed in full in D4.3 Report on the Quality Assurance Methodology. This deliverable covers the various aspects of quality and quality assurance related to SPECTRO and defines the methodology to assess and mitigate risks during the execution of the project.

In particular, the deliverable specifies the quality guidelines to be followed in the production of deliverables. The Quality Manager (QM) is responsible for supervising the deliverable review process from start to end, establishing the review process dates. They also support the peer reviewers and Deliverable Team during the deliverable review process.

D4.3 also details the Quality and Assurance Methodology adopted by SPECTRO to assess the quality of the two educational programmes. Such methodology has two main purposes:

1. To guarantee high-quality content and management to secure effective progress.
2. to adopt quality assurance standards to the two education programmes and specify a methodology to periodically assess the achievement of such standards.

The deliverable also covers the risk issues specifying the methodology adopted to assess risks and mitigate them.

The Quality Assurance Manager of the SPECTRO project is Bruno Crispo – Bruno.crispo@unitn.it

The Data Protection Officer of the project can be contacted at privacy@eitdigital.eu

5.1 Deliverables

Please refer to D4.3 Section 2 “Quality guidelines on deliverable production” for details on the quality criteria and deliverable review process.

6 Financial support to students

SPECTRO provides eligible students the financial support to take part to the education programmes and offers scholarship programmes to promote diversity in terms of gender, age, social and economic background. SPECTRO’s scholarships allow the greatest number to have access to high-quality education in digital areas and increase diversity among students and future digital experts. The students awarded a scholarship will be financially supported during their two years of studies in one of the double-degree in Masters’ programmes offered by SPECTRO.

6.1 Eligible countries

The SPECTRO scholarship programme is open to students who are nationals of eligible countries, specifically those belonging to EU Member States, overseas countries and territories (OCTs), countries associated with the Digital Europe Programme.

6.2 Eligible recipients

To qualify for financial support, students must first be enrolled and accepted into one of the two double-degree Master’s programmes offered by SPECTRO—in Cybersecurity or Robotics. Scholarships are awarded exclusively to those who meet these criteria and who demonstrate merit through a rigorous selection process. Merit is assessed primarily through the candidate’s academic path to date, especially their performance in their bachelor’s studies, and is evaluated as part of the selection process that precedes admission to the Master’s programme.

6.3 Activities to be funded

The financial support provided through the SPECTRO scholarship programme is intended to enable student participation in the two-year double-degree Master's programmes. Funded activities include tuition fee coverage and, in some cases, living support to facilitate student mobility and engagement across partner universities.

Three types of scholarships are available:

- (1) **Scholarships of Excellence**, which include a full tuition fee waiver and a monthly living allowance adjusted according to the cost-of-living index of the host country (this adjustment is computed using the "Correction coefficients" published by Eurostat on its website);
- (2) **Full Tuition Fee Waivers**, covering the entire tuition cost for both years; and
- (3) **Half Tuition Fee Waivers**, which cover 50% of the tuition costs. These funding schemes are designed to reduce financial barriers and support talented students in accessing high-quality education in key digital technology domains.

The maximum financial support available per student depends on the type of scholarship awarded. The Scholarship of Excellence includes a full tuition fee waiver valued at €5,000 per academic year (€10,000 for the two years) and a monthly living allowance of €900, adjusted based on the Country Correction Coefficient (CCC) of the study location. Over the two years, this may result in a total support package exceeding €25,000 per student. Students receiving a Full Tuition Fee Waiver are granted €5,000 per year (€10,000 for the two years), while those with a Half Tuition Fee Waiver receive €2,500 per year (€5,000 for the two years).

In all cases, 50% of the financial support will be directly financed by the EU through the SPECTRO grant, while the remaining 50% will be financed to students by the co-financing component provided by the EIT Digital Education Foundation.

6.4 Maximum amount per student and criteria for its determination

The SPECTRO project foresees the allocation of 150 financial support packages (scholarships) to students enrolled in its two Master's programmes over the course of the project. These scholarships will be evenly distributed across the two programme cycles, with approximately 75 scholarships allocated in Cycle 1 (academic years 2024–2026) and 75 in Cycle 2 (academic years 2025–2027).

Each year, the scholarship allocation process will take place before the application and evaluation phase, aligned with the issuance of the admission letters. Scholarships are composed of two distinct components:

- Tuition fee waivers (half or full), which are not paid directly to students but applied as a reduction of the tuition cost. The value of the waiver is determined before the start of Year 1 and covers both academic years of the programme. Students are invoiced for tuition fees twice per academic year—once in the fall semester and once in the spring semester. For students receiving financial support, the invoices will reflect the reduced tuition amount, and this is the moment when the support is formally materialised.
- Monthly allowances (only for recipients of the Scholarship of Excellence), which are paid directly to students to support their living costs. These monthly payments are calculated based on the Country Correction Coefficient (CCC) of the country where the student is studying, and may vary between Year 1 and Year 2 depending on the country of study for the supported student.

This structure ensures both administrative clarity and financial predictability for students throughout their studies.

6.5 Minimum number of students

The minimum number of students to receive scholarships is 150 over the duration of the project. These scholarships will be evenly distributed across the two Master's programmes (Cybersecurity and Robotics), which implies approximately 37 or 38 students per programme, per cycle.

At a high level, the scholarships in each cycle will be split across the three categories as follows:

- Scholarships of Excellence (full waiver and allowance): ~6–7 per programme per cycle
- Full Tuition Fee Waivers: ~12–14 per programme per cycle
- Half Tuition Fee Waivers: ~18–20 per programme per cycle

This initial distribution is indicative and will be refined during each recruitment cycle based on the profile of applicants, strategic priorities (e.g. gender balance, RIS representation), available budget, and decisions made collectively at project level by the consortium. The goal is to ensure both fairness and strategic alignment while maintaining high levels of programme participation and diversity.

6.6 How to apply

To apply to a SPECTRO scholarship, candidates must enrol into one of SPECTRO two master's programmes.

Enrolment is done via a single application portal. When enrolling to one of the two master's programmes, applicants are given the opportunity to select 3 options as Entry University and 3 options as Exit University with order of priority. It gives students a wider choice: applicants who would not be accepted to their preferred education institution might still be accepted by another education institution. At the same time, as the capacity of each education institution is limited, the multiple-option offer ensures that a high number of applications is processed.

To apply to the two SPECTRO Master's programme, candidates are required to upload into the application portal the following documentation:

- **Degree Certificate/Diploma** in its original language and translated into English (If your university does not provide this service, the translation has to be done by an authorised translator and his/her credentials, signature and stamps must be visible in the translated document). In case of ongoing studies, a statement certifying that you are in the final year of your studies. The statement must be written by the degree administration office (or equivalent department) confirming that you are enrolled on the final year of your education and giving your expected completion date.
- **Official and stamped transcript of records in original language and translated into English.** All courses taken must be included. Please scan the front and back of every document- all stamps and signatures must be fully visible.
- **Proof of English proficiency.** The requirement of English proficiency will vary depending on the higher education institution/country selected by the applicant. Please refer to EITD Master School website 'Admissions' tab for more information.
- **Curriculum Vitae** including details on your academic and professional career.
- **A letter of motivation** (maximum 3 pages) to prove the innovative potential of the applicant and their need for financial support. In this letter applicants will be required to discuss and/or propose an entrepreneurial idea and to explain their financial situation and need for financial support.
- **Supporting documents regarding the applicant's financial situation** (e.g. credit report).
- **An official ID**, such as passport or National ID.
- The allocation of scholarships will be done at the end of the selection process and before sending the letter of acceptance.

6.7 Awarding criteria

The type and amount of financial support awarded to each student are determined through a structured, transparent, and merit-based evaluation process. Each eligible applicant is assigned a merit score on a scale from 1 to 5, which serves as the primary reference point for ranking and scholarship allocation.

This score is based on three core elements:

1. Academic and professional background, with a particular emphasis on the performance in the applicant's bachelor's degree;
2. Curriculum Vitae, including any relevant work experience, extracurricular activities, and achievements;
3. Motivation letter, in which candidates are expected to describe their motivation for applying to the programme, propose an entrepreneurial idea, and explain their financial situation and need for support.

The merit score is initially assigned by two independent evaluators: the Local Programme Coordinators from the Entry and Exit universities selected by the applicant. These evaluations are then reviewed and harmonised by the Programme Leaders and the Quality Assurance Manager to ensure consistency across institutions and countries. Final scholarship decisions are taken jointly during a dedicated selection meeting involving all relevant academic and administrative stakeholders.

In addition to the merit score, scholarship awarding criteria include:

- Promotion of diversity and inclusion, with priority given to female applicants and applicants from EIT Regional Innovation Scheme (RIS) countries;
- Balance of scholarship distribution across partner universities and countries to maintain equity and ensure efficient use of available capacity.

6.7.1 Promotion of diversity

The SPECTRO scholarship programme will thrive to promote diversity and inclusion through its scholarship opportunities:

- Priority will be given to female applicants from any EU country or EU-associated country. The scholarship programme for women will aim increase female participation in master's programmes in Cybersecurity and Robotics.

- Priority will be given to applicants from RIS countries - included in the EIT Regional Innovation Scheme (RIS). The scholarship programme for participants from RIS countries is aimed to support the participation of students from countries with moderate or modest innovation score and with lower gross domestic product. Countries eligible to take part to the RIS include 1) EU members states, 2) Horizon Europe associated countries, and 3) outermost regions such as Guadeloupe, and Réunion (France), the Azores and Madeira (Portugal), and the Canary Islands (Spain).

Appendix A – Template for progress report

SPECTRO Quarterly Progress Report

[PARTNER NAME]- M# to M#

TECHNICAL PROGRESS	
How are you progressing with your work? (Please provide a short overall impression of the progress of your work – max 5 lines).	
Please outline the contribution you made to work package(s) (WP) in the last month (max 3 items).	
WP1	
WP2	
WP3	
WP4	
Please outline the contribution you foresee making over the next month (max 3 items).	
WP1	
WP2	
WP3	
WP4	
Are you encountering or do you anticipate problems achieving formal results/deliverables?	
WP1	
WP2	
WP3	
WP4	
Are you encountering or do you anticipate problems fulfilling your informal commitments? (For example, providing informal input for other work packages)	
Are you encountering or do you anticipate problems meeting your deadline (are you running into time problems?)	
Are you encountering or do you anticipate any budgetary problems (person month allocation and financial budget)?	
Meeting participation and event attendance (please describe all meetings or events participated by some partner's member for the interest of the project):	

Appendix B – Template for reporting expenses

The collection of data regarding PM allocation and expenses will happen quarterly with a declaration from all participant partners. The collection of this data will happen via an exchange of an Excel from all project participants with the PM, after his request. The excel template can be found on the SPECTRO Project Team Drive on Microsoft Teams.

The information collected will be the following:

SPECTRO Quarterly Expenses Report

[PARTNER NAME]- M# to M#

INTERNAL MANPOWER				
Employee Name	Activity / Task	PMs	Monthly rate	Activity / Task Description
<i>Name Surname</i>	<i>WP# - T#.#</i>	<i># PM</i>	<i>€ ###,##0.00</i>	<i>Task description.</i>

OTHER COSTS (including Travel and Subsistence)			
Activity / Task	Cost Type	Amount	Cost Description
<i>WP# - T#.#</i>	<i>Travel and Subsistence / Other goods, works and services</i>	<i>€ ###,##0.00</i>	<i>Description of the cost.</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>For travel and subsistence: name of person travelling, date and destination and purpose of travel.</i> ▪ <i>For Other goods, works and services: description of the good, work or service, cost/value and date of invoice.</i>

References

[DIGITAL] <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/activities/digital-programme>

[SPECTRO] <http://eitdigital.eu/spectro/>

Glossary

Community	A group of users, organised with a common purpose, and jointly granted access to resources. It may act as the interface between individual users and the resources. (see also [WISE-SCI])
EC	European Commission
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
KIC	Knowledge and Innovation Community
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
R&S	Research and scholarship